

SSHOC'n Tell Challenge

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The SSH Open Marketplace Pelican

Trying out

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What

Among the best practice of a Digital Humanities (DH) engineer, or researcher as well, is the urge to always be updated on the last technologies, discoveries or innovations. As we work on a domain in constant evolution, we need to be aware each day of publications made all around the world. But the large amount of publications available on various repositories all day and the difficulty to find articles and datasets related closely to my own topic of work is a pain. Automate topic-related publications and datasets gathering through API crawling of the SSH Open Marketplace and others platform solves greatly this problem: on the one hand references are gathered on a website in a database as a future reading, on the other hand a twitter bot increases serendipity by sharing all days some articles or datasets dedicated to a specific theme in one twitter's timeline.

Who

I'm a data engineer working at the ERC PuppetPlays project (GA835193) directed by Didier Plassard, professor in Drama and Performance studies, and hosted by the University Paul-Valéry Montpellier 3 (France). The project aims to reappraise Western European Repertoires for Puppet and Marionette Theatres and bring into the light this almost invisible repertoire. Working there, I'm aware of the difficulty to find quality publications and datasets related to popular art, more generally lesser studied one. Creating an open source and well-documented app that crawls platform through API can help research communities to be aware about publications dedicated to their research topic.

How

I plan to use the SSH Open Marketplace API, both requests `get/api/datasets` and `get/api/publication`. Getting those lists of JSON data, I will make a query on the `{label}` and the `{description}` to search specific terms. For each dataset or publication that fits into my query, I get informations into both the `{AccessibleAt}` and `{source{url}}` JSON values to get then access manually to the document or dataset.

When

I will soon develop my API script with Python and check which dataset or publication are dedicated to popular literature. The longer part of development will be to integrate others API to mix sources to enrich my survey on this subject.

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www.sshopencloud.eu

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